

Notas breves

New images of the soft parts of *Skenea serpuloides* (Prosobranchia, Turbinidae)

Nuevas imágenes de las partes blandas de *Skenea serpuloides* (Prosobranchia, Turbinidae)

Federico RUBIO* and Emilio ROLÁN**

Recibido el 18-VII-2012. Aceptado el 6-X-2012

INTRODUCTION

At present the subfamily Skeneinae (Prosobranchia) family Turbinidae includes 42 genera, their several species inhabiting every sea, from the lower intertidal level down to abyssal depths. It has been always considered a polyphyletic group of species, characterized by its extremely reduced size and the lack of a nacreous layer. Nevertheless, as further study has been done on the anatomy and radula of many such

species, quite a few of them have been transferred to other families.

The poor knowledge of animals of Skeneinae species is the reason why we decided to show the SEM images obtained using the technique of critical-point dried specimens of *Skenea serpuloides* (Fleming, 1825), type species of the genus, from which only the brief anatomical description provided by FRETTER & GRAHAM (1977) was known.

RESULTS

Genus *Skenea* Fleming, 1825

Skenea Fleming, 1825. *Edinburgh Philosophical Journal*, 12: 246. [Type species, subsequent designation by Gray (1847): *Helix serpuloides* Montagu, 1808, Great Britain].

Delphinoidea Brown, 1827. [Type species by subsequent designation Gray (1847): *Helix serpuloides* Montagu, 1808].

Remarks: VAN AARTSEN, MENKHORST & GITTEBERGER (1984) were the first to present SEM photographs of the shell of *Skenea serpuloides* from Algeciras Bay.

WARÉN (1991) also provided SEM photographs of shell, operculum and radula. RUBIO-SALAZAR (1991: 189) provided a drawing of the animal, detailing

* Pintor Ribera, 4-16^a, 46930 Quart de Poblet (Valencia), federubio@ono.com

** Museo de Historia Natural, Campus Universitario Sur, 15782, Santiago de Compostela, Spain, erolan@emiliorolan.com

Figure 1. *Skenea serpuloides*, soft parts in anterior view. Abbreviations, ct: cephalic tentacle; el: eye-lobes; et3, et4: epipodial tentacles 3 and 4; o: operculum; pp: propodial penis; sn: snout.

Figura 1. *Skenea serpuloides*, partes blandas vistas desde la parte anterior. Abreviaturas, ct: tentáculo cefálico; el: lóbulos oculares; et3, et4: tentáculos epipodiales 3 y 4; o: opérculo; pp: pene propodial; sn: hocico.

its different organs. However, nothing has been published so far as SEM pho-

tographs of the animal of *S. serpuloides*, which we present below.

Skenea serpuloides (Montagu, 1808)

Helix serpuloides Montagu, 1808. *Testacea Britannica* – Supplement, p. 147, pl. 21 fig. 3.

Material examined: 10 sps, from Limens, Ria de Vigo, dredged at 15-20 m, in maërl bottom.

Description: Soft parts (Figs. 1-3). The snout (SN) is long and broad apically. There are no anterior cephalic lappets. The cephalic tentacles (CT) are long and slender and are at least twice as long as the snout in some specimens; they are covered by sensory papillae ciliated distally (Fig. 3A). The eye-lobes (EL) are reduced to an inconspicuous lateral fold at the base of the cephalic tentacles. On the right side the eye-lobe is continuous

with a single tentacle of one-third of the size of the cephalic one, distally with strongly ciliated edges (PT - postocular tentacle).

Neck lobes wide, ciliated, with a smooth margin; in both neck-lobes the cilia are distributed on the outer edge; the right neck-lobe (RNL) is long and curved distally while the left neck-lobe (LNL) widens much distally becoming spatulate in shape.

Figure 2. *Skenea serpuloides*, soft parts. A: ventral view; B: view from left side; C: view from right side. Abbreviations, ct: cephalic tentacle; el: eye-lobes; et1, et2, et3, et4: epipodial tentacles 1-4; lnl: left neck lobe; o: operculum; pp: propodial penis; pt: postocular tentacle; rnl: right neck lobe; sn: snout. *Figura 2. Skenea serpuloides, partes blandas. A: vista ventral; B: vista desde el lado izquierdo; C: vista desde el lado derecho. Abreviaturas: ct: tentáculo cefálico; el: lóbulos oculares; et1, et2, et3, et4: tentáculos epipodiales 1-4; lnl: lóbulo cervical izquierdo; o: opérculo; pp: pene propodial; pt: tentáculo postocular; rnl: lóbulo cervical derecho; sn: hocico.*

Four epipodial tentacles (ET) on each side of the foot can be seen behind the neck-lobes. The epipodial tentacles are shorter and narrower than the cephalic ones and are distally covered by sensory papillae, although in lesser numbers. The second epipodial tentacles, located at their base and more evident on the right side of the foot, are much shorter than the

first ones; the tentacle on the left side passes almost unnoticed. The third and fourth tentacles are placed on each side under the operculum.

The foot is large, flat, truncated anteriorly, rounded posteriorly, with a large propodium, which has a large penis (PP), very thick, cylindrical-shaped, which shows a deep channel that runs

Figure 3. *Skenea serpuloides*, partial views of soft parts. A: detail of cephalic tentacle showing the distally ciliated sensory papillae; B: caudal view. Abbreviations, ct: cephalic tentacle; et4: fourth epipodial tentacles; o: operculum; mp: metapodium.

Figura 3. *Skenea serpuloides*, vistas parciales de las partes blandas. A: detalle del tentáculo cefálico mostrando las papilas sensoriales ciliadas en su parte distal; B: vista posterior. Abreviaturas: ct: tentáculo cefálico; et4: cuartos tentáculos epipodiales; o: opérculo; mp: metapodio.

completely along its length and has thick bumps on each side; the channel ends on the right side of the penis near the outer end.

The mesopodium and metapodium show randomly distributed groups of cilia. The metapodium (MP) has a deep groove that divides it in two; both sides come together at the more distal end, next to the sole. This character has not been observed in any other known species of *Skeneinae*.

Remarks: In relation to *Skenea serpuloides*, FRETTER & GRAHAM (1977) indicate the presence of a penis behind the right eye-lobe, but this appendage is a postocular tentacle, which lies between the right eye-lobe and neck-lobe. Although WARÉN & BOUCHET (1993: 22) indicate that this postocular tentacle is absent in *Dikoleps nitens*, RUBIO, DANTART & LUQUE (1998, 2004) demonstrated its existence.

An important synapomorphy of at least a part of the family is the large

and, in this species, cylindrical and grooved propodial penis. Its size and shape varies from one species to another but it is present in all species of the genus *Dikoleps* (RUBIO, DANTART & LUQUE, 1998, 2004); we have also verified its presence in the type species of the genera *Skeneoides* (*Skeneoides exilisima* (Philippi, 1844)) and *Pseudorbis* (*Pseudorbis granulum* (Brugnone, 1873)). This propodial penis has been observed in others genera such as: *Protolira* Warén & Bouchet, 1993 and *Bruceiella* Warén & Bouchet, 1993.

According to WARÉN & BOUCHET (1993: 22), in this species there were individuals found to be simultaneous hermaphrodites, which is in agreement with the interpretation of this propodial structure as a penis.

Another differential character is the deep furrow that divides the metapodium in two parts, which only come together at the outer edge of the foot, next to the sole.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The late Lluís Dantart made the critical-point photographs some years ago.

António A. Monteiro revised the manuscript.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- FLEMING J. 1825. On the British testaceous Annelids. *Edinburgh Philosophical Journal*, 12: 238-248.
- FRETTER V. & GRAHAM A. 1977. The Prosobranch molluscs of Britain and Denmark. Part 2 - Trochacea. *Journal of Molluscan Studies, Supplement 3*: 39-100.
- RUBIO-SALAZAR F. 1991. Skeneidos infra y cirralitorales de las costas del sur y levante español. *Iberus* 9(1-2):187-202.
- RUBIO F., DANTART L. & LUQUE A.A. 1998. Two new species of *Dikoleps* (Gastropoda, Skeneidae) from the Mediterranean coast of Spain. *Iberus*, 16(1): 81-93.
- RUBIO F., DANTART L. & LUQUE A., 2004. El género *Dikoleps* (Gastropoda, Skeneidae) en las costas ibéricas. *Iberus*, 22(1): 113-132.
- VAN AARTSEN J.J., MENKHORST H.P.M.G. & GITTENBERGER E. 1984. The marine molluscs of the Bay of Algeciras, Spain, with general notes on *Mitrella*, Marginellidae and Turridae. *Basteria, Supplement 2*, 135 pp.
- WARÉN A. 1991. New and little known mollusca from Iceland and Scandinavia. *Sarsia*, 76: 53-124.
- WARÉN A. & BOUCHET P. 1993. New, records, species, genera, and a new family of gastropods from hydrothermal vents and hydrocarbon seeps. *Zoologica Scripta*, 22: 1-90.

